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Enhancing EV user experience in eCharge4Drivers project: the case of the metropolitan city of Bari

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Abstract The Electric Vehicles (EVs) are progressively diffusing around the world aiming at substituting the internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles in the next years. To make it reliable and close the market of ICE vehicles by 2035 according to the 2050 decarbonization objectives, in Europe, several initiatives and research and innovation programme are ongoing. In the context of the H2020 EU eCharge4Drivers project¹, in a user-centric perspective, this paper presents enhanced services to improve the charging and traveling experience of EV end users. The case study of the Metropolitan City of Bari (Italy) is considered in which the pilot demonstrations are based on the use of enhanced and interoperable services such as booking, route planning and new incentives schemes. The preliminary results of the pilot tests are described as well as the a-priori user's perception of the proposed solutions using the Kano model analysis.

Keywords: Electric Mobility, EV user, charge point booking, route planning, incentive schemes

1. Introduction

Over the past decade, addressing the impact of transportation on climate change has suddenly become a focal point for a global scale, by mobilizing international efforts to combat climate change through the decarbonization of transportation. The Paris Agreement, adopted in 2015, serves as a landmark accord where nations committed to limiting global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels [1]. The European Union (EU) has taken a proactive position in setting ambitious decarbonization objectives for the transportation sector. One of the primary goals is to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 year [2], with a particular emphasis on reducing emissions from road, air, and maritime transport. In this sense, the EU has envisaged a global transition towards sustainable, low-carbon mobility, driven by technological advances, increased use of renewable energy sources and innovative policy measures [3]. One of the key objectives for the decarbonization of transportation is the Electrification of Vehicles. With this aim, among other activities, the EU has promoted and co-funded Horizon research projects, which are responding with new perspectives and solutions for the widespread adoption of electric vehicles. This contribution will focus on the research project supported by the

¹ This manuscript reflects only the authors views and opinions, neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be considered responsible for them.

European Union's Horizon 2020 research, the eCharge4Drivers project (eC4D), under grant agreement No 875131 [4]. The ongoing eC4D project, works to substantially improve the EV charging experience within cities and for long trips. The project is developing and demonstrating user-friendly charging stations and innovative charging solutions as well as smart charging services for the users. By capturing users' perceptions and expectations on the various charging options and their mobility and parking habits, eC4D is in demonstration phase in among 10 areas across Europe, including metropolitan areas and Trans-European Transport Network (TEN-T) corridors. This work will analyze the first results of the Bari demonstration pilot site in eC4D context, with its specific use cases implementation.

The structure of the paper is the following. Section 2 describes the enhanced and interoperable services for the EV users and Section 3 reports the results obtained in the Bari demonstration pilot. Finally, Section 3 discusses the conclusions.

2. Enhanced and interoperable services for the EV users

In the eC4D project, different services have been developed to meet the EV user needs and improve their traveling and charging experience. In this paper, the following three user-centric services are described.

2.1 Enhanced booking service

A new booking service is conceived for a reliable reservation of the available charging stations. A convenient booking service is intended to exploit the use of this limited resource in an efficient manner, especially with the increasing use of EVs. To avoid overlapping of charging requests and other operational issues, it is essential to design the booking service tool from a practical viewpoint and with a strong user-centric perspective. To this purpose, the booking service is designed to facilitate EV users to reserve a charging solution based on their charging preferences and travel needs. It is important to enable the user selecting, from a list of available charging stations, the most preferable one in terms of technology, distance, availability, energy costs and mobility needs.

The high-level functionalities and features offered by the booking service can be listed as follows:

- Create and manage a user profile that includes charging preferences.
- Create and manage a vehicle profile including information such as the vehicle brand/model, the battery capacity, the plug type/s, estimated full autonomy and create and manage a list of favorite chargers.
- Book now (in short-term period, e.g., at most 15-20 minutes ahead) or book in long term options (e.g. up to 24 hours ahead). If a selected CP is booked shortly before the starting of the charging session, once the booking is validated, the user must reach the CP within that short time. Long-term booking can be advantageous for long distance trips in which having stops planned and reserved in advance makes the travel experience significantly more satisfying.
- Book a slow or fast DC charge point.
- Authentication and Payment services by RFID or mobile application.
- Receive notification about the real-time and predicted occupancy of the charger and of its parking spot. It is important to warn the user that is approaching a CP about the availability of the charger and of the

parking spot in order to avoid undesired waiting in front of an occupied CP. The Booking Service should consider all the details from the current charging session and the following bookings: for instance, the user that is charging receives a warning a few minutes before the charging session is over (this warning can be received by a pop-up notification); a user who wants to start charging in a CP that is booked a few minutes from then also receives a warning.

- Booking calendar management; planned and historic booking sessions information.
- Incentives for a reliable booking: users can be incentivized to make a fair and ethical use of the service and do not violate the booking session period to avoid overlapping of the charging sessions.

Short-term and long-term reservations are both considered with specific functional and nonfunctional requirements and restrictions for serving different mobility needs (i.e., urban mobility, inter-city and long trips). The booking service is hosted by the electromobility service provider (eMSP) back-end system and is offered to the final user through a mobile application for iOS and Android devices.

The booking service offers visualized enhanced information to the user before, during and after the charging sessions aiming to improve the charging experience of the users and allow them to be more actively involved in the charging process. In case the selected CP is not available in the desired period, the user can decide between waiting or choosing another available CP. In the former case, the booking service manages the booking queue according to the “First in First Out” service policy. In this case the CP is inhibited for other users only 15 minutes before the starting. If a reserved CP or its parking bay is occupied by other users during the reservation period, tracked either by the CP status from the CPO back-end system or via parking sensors, the booking service notifies the user who has reserved the CP a few minutes before the charging session starting about this inconvenience and alternative solutions are offered to him/her, as for example, a discount for the next charging session or a back-up CP booking. To prevent the improper use of the booking service and the CP, different penalty/reward policies can be applied by the CPOs/eMSPs as will be described in Section 2.3.

Figure 1 Booking service: screenshots from the mobile app.

2.2 Enhanced route planner

The enhanced route planner focuses on planning the EV trip including the charging stops according to the user profile and preferences, based on advanced energy consumption prediction models and algorithms. Special

attention is paid to route planning of long trips, which necessitate multiple stops to be aligned with user preferences. The main functionalities offered by the service can be categorized as follows:

- User profile and preferences: EV characteristics (e.g., Vehicle type, plug type, Charging power); general preferences (e.g., Renewable Energy Source CP Usage, Tariff); journey preferences (e.g., Points of Interest (PoI); State of Charging (SoC), Dynamic Route Recommender)
- Occupancy in real-time showing the current status of the selected CPs on the screen of the user.
- Occupancy prediction.
- Pop-up notifications: the CP the user is heading to gets occupied or when the dynamic route recommender has any recommendation.
- Other information e.g., Weather and Charging Point Information.
- Algorithms: main routing algorithm (e.g., multiple stops, long and short distance navigation); optimize the route according to the user specified requirements and characteristics, allowing the user to include additional stops; multiple requests (recommendation, information sharing) management, dynamically being able to recommend other CPs when the App receives multiple requests for a specific CP; Navigation (e.g., Traffic status, Dynamic Route Recommender); SoC Estimator.

The routing service is offered via a web tool to plan offline the route and via a mobile application in order to be navigated according to the plan. In Figure 2, some screenshots from the web tool are provided indicating some of the input data needed from the end users to optimize the route planning based on the preferences. In particular, start time, start and destination points are needed, and the user can further select waypoints to be visited in between. Moreover, the initial SoC is needed as input and the final desired SoC can be selected. User can also give priority to different point of interest to be visited while charging like restaurants (food), nature points (park, etc.), shops. These priority weights are used by the implemented algorithms to plan the route accordingly.

Figure 2 Route planner: webtool pages for input data.

2.3 Incentives Management Platform

An incentive management platform (IMP) has been designed and prepared to manage a dynamic system of rewards and penalties linked to the use of the booking service.

The idea is to create an IT platform to incentivize the users to make a fair use of the booked charging stations. The fair (unfair) use of the booking service is regulated by the service provider and CPO according to specific

positive (negative) behaviors expected from the end users while using the reservation service, as reported in the terms of use of the application. The IMP policy is based on the booking service terms of use, and it implements specific “game rules” to establish if the user merits rewards or penalties. The IMP thus is designed to be connected to the charging station booking service platform in Bari. Therefore, the user of the booking service is asked when registering to agree or disagree with the IMP policy. In case of user agreement, the user of booking service can join the IMP platform and based on the game rules, the user will be rewarded (penalized) with a positive (negative) score, called GreenPoint (or GP), which can be used to redeem a reward in terms of charging/booking discount tickets, ticket restaurant, local shops discount, gift cards, etc.

In the following a list of some of the game rules is specified to manage the GPs assignment:

- Reward in case of a cancelled booking session due to an overlap (+1GP).
- Make a successful booking session for 5 consecutive times (+3GP).

A list of rules defined for the cancellation of GPs is reported as follows:

- Cancel a booking session in short term (-1GP).
- Exceed the booking session time (over a grace period) while charging (-1GP).
- Exceed the booking session time (over a grace period) while not charging (-2GP).
- Do not use a booked charging station (-2GP).

The positive balance of GPs can be converted into rewards as previously mentioned, according to specific CP targets to be achieved as defined in the application terms of use. Some screenshots from the mobile application which will be offered to the users are given in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Incentive service: screenshots from the mobile app prototype.

3. The case study in the metropolitan city of Bari

The metropolitan city of Bari is the capital city of the Apulia region in the southern Italy. In eC4D project context, the metropolitan city of Bari is one of 10 demonstration areas across Europe. For this pilot site, the implementation of the enhanced route planner, booking service and the IMP is an ongoing activity for which we would like to present the preliminary results and the user perception. The a-priori user perception towards the services described in Section 2 is analyzed in this section. To get the user perception we adopt the Kano model [5] and we can provide the analysis of the results for the booking and routing services. Penalties and

rewards policies are also evaluated among the booking service features. In particular, the Kano model offers a reliable, comprehensible, and standardized way of classifying the features into groups, but also a way of prioritizing each of the relevant features. This method consists in asking the user how they would feel if a certain feature is present and how they would feel if it is not present. The results of the survey give us a classification of the features in the following groups:

- **Must-be (M)** – basic expectations, threshold: The product features are simply expected by customers. If the product does not have them, it will be incomplete or just plain bad. The existence of these features will not make the customers more satisfied (basic expectations).
- **Performance (P)** – one dimension: A feature in this category is seen as the more present, the better. Along with two attributes (i.e., satisfaction, functionality). Every increase in functionality leads to increased satisfaction.
- **Attractive (A)** – exciting, experimental: these are the unexpected features whose absence does not generate dissatisfaction, but their presence satisfies the customer. From mild attractiveness to absolute delight, all ranges fit under the “Attractive” name.
- **Indifferent Quality (I)** - indifferent: the presence of absence of these attributes do not cause any satisfaction or dissatisfaction in the clients.
- **Reverse (R)** - rejection: the presence of these attributes causes dissatisfaction among customers, and their absence produces satisfaction.
- **Questionable (Q)** – not logical: this is not a quality category, but a classification element to represent an error in the interpretation of the questions. It represents the conflict responses, for instance “I like it” for both “feature absent” and “feature present”.

To discover the customer’s perceptions towards the product’s attributes, the Kano questionnaire is needed. The Kano Model has its own standard questionnaire format, which is based on two kinds of questions done for each feature: a) How would you feel if the service feature is present? (Functional form); b) How would you feel if the service feature is absent? (Dysfunctional form). In both cases the possible answers are the following ones: *I like it; I expect it; I don’t care; I can tolerate it; I dislike it.*

In the following sections we present the preliminary results of the demonstrations of the route planner and booking services including the Kano analysis. The Kano survey has been submitted to targeted EV users in the city of Bari. In Table 1 and 3, the functionalities/features evaluated in the user survey for the routing and booking service are respectively reported. A total number of 130 responses have been received and analyzed by using the discrete analysis approach based on the six-groups (M, P, A, I, R, Q) classification previously described [5].

3.1 Enhanced route planner

3.1.1 Kano survey analysis

In Table 1, the functionalities/features of the routing service evaluated in the user survey are reported in detail.

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To analyze the survey responses the discrete approach of Kano Model has been applied and the results are reported in Table 2.

Table 1. Functionalities analysed in the Kano survey for the Route Planner

Code	Functionality
RP01	There is an option of setting up some general preferences (tariff, renewable energy source, power of CP)
RP02	The prediction of the CP occupancy at the estimated time of arrival at the CP is displayed
RP03	SoC* is set to a fixed value by the system (e.g., 50%) although you could provide it every time you create a route. *The State of Charge (SoC) estimation helps determine the number of stops a driver needs to do, ensuring that the driver will not run out of battery.
RP04	The Route Planner provides an approximate estimation of the SoC that you will have when you arrive to the next charging point
RP05	The Route Planner provides the areas where you should stop for charging, and allows you to make the final decision on which specific CP to charge, while displaying a number of potential CPs
RP06	The Route Planner allows you to introduce the maximum time you want to spend at the CPs? With this info, the No of stops can vary
RP07	The Route Planner asks you to adapt/switch the route through a pop-up notification
RP08	The Route Planner drives you to a CP that is not busy
RP09	The Route Planner has a button for direct route to the closest CP while you are on navigation mode
RP10	The Route Planner allows you to book the CP you are navigating within 15 minutes before arriving

Table 2. Discrete analysis for the route planner in Bari.

CODE	M	P	A	I	Q	R	CATEGORY
RP01	10	0	70	50	0	0	Attractive
RP02	20	10	40	50	0	10	Indifferent
RP03	10	10	50	60	0	0	Indifferent
RP04	30	0	50	50	0	0	Attr. / Ind.
RP05	30	50	40	10	0	0	Performance
RP06	0	10	60	60	0	0	Attr. / Ind.
RP07	0	0	90	40	0	0	Attractive
RP08	50	60	10	10	0	0	Performance
RP09	10	10	70	40	0	0	Attractive
RP10	10	0	80	40	0	0	Attractive

From Table 2, it can be concluded that for the responders there are functionalities that will increase the performance of the service like RP05 and RP08 and attractive functionalities like RP01, RP07, RP09 and RP10.

3.1.2 Demonstration test

Recently, the demonstration of the service has been launched for the customers of the Apulia Region. As today, 15 customers have used the route planner web tool to plan long distance trips and one of these trips is described

in the following as example. As described in Section 2, the enhanced route planner² basic input from the user are the origin and destination addresses, the type of vehicle, and the starting and ending State of Charge (SoC) of the battery. In a user-friendly manner the web tool allows the user to prioritize stops based on his/her preferences, eventually inserting waypoints such as night, lunch or pass stop and selecting alternative CPs and plug type. In this way, the user can plan the trip on the basis of personal needs.

Figure 4 User trip with web tool: option A and B.

Table 3 Option A, B details

	Trip Stops	Waypoint Type	Connector Type	CP name	Stop Address	Start SoC	Charge Time	End SoC
Option A	Stop 1	Night	type2 - 22 Kw	IT*ENX*E19XP22T 3KK4AH00514*2	Lungomare Vittorio Emanuele III, Taranto	26,40%	09h 23m	100%
	Stop 2	Charge	type2 - 22 Kw	IT*ENX*E18XP22T 5AB5U000148*1	Via Matteotti 132, Bitonto (BA)	75,30%	00h 53m	88,40%
Option B	Stop 1	Night	type2 - 22 Kw	IT*ENX*E19XP22T 3KK4AH00342*1	Via Stella Polare – Torrecanne (BR)	20,20%	09h 31m	100%
	Stop 2	Charge	type2 - 22 Kw	IT*ENX*E18XP22T 5AB5U000148*1	Via Matteotti 132, Bitonto (BA)	79,20%	00h 37m	88,40%

The considered trip in the Apulia region (see Figure 4) is of about 400 Km. The trip starts at 7 p.m. CET, with commercial EV having average 250 km range of battery. This trip starts from Ugento (Lecce) and San Giovanni Rotondo (Foggia) is the destination. In this case, based on specific needs, the EV user wants to start and end the trip with the same SoC battery level (> 50%). The route planner returns two possible route options (A, B as in Figure 4), including urban and extra-urban paths, whose details are reported in Table 3. Two night stops for a long charging are suggested close to hotels, as required by the user.

² The enhanced route planner service has been developed by ICOOR (Interuniversity Consortium for Optimization and Operation Research).

3.2 Enhanced booking service

In Table 4, the functionalities/features of the booking service evaluated in the user survey are reported in detail. To analyze the survey responses, the discrete approach of Kano Model has been applied and the results of the analysis are reported in Table 5.

Table 4. Functionalities analysed for the Booking Service

Code	Functionality
BS01	A penalization to customers that make a wrong use of the booking service (e.g., keeping charging besides the booked session and blocking charge sessions to the next customers; arriving late at the booked CP). Example of penalties are economic, losing charging session.
BS02	A compensation to customers that are unable to charge at the booked charging point because it is improperly occupied by another customer? Example of compensations are discount on charging, booking a back-up CP.
BS03	Book a CP in a short-term period (e.g. by 15 minutes)
BS04	Book a CP in a long-term period (e.g. from 2 hours to 1 week ahead)
BS05	Book a CP based on the prediction of occupancy in the future
BS06	Receive real time information about the CP (e.g. CP availability, parking occupation) and the charging session (e.g. charge speed, cost)
BS07	Save and have information about your favorite chargers
BS08	Choose among different payment options? (e.g. card, mobile app...)
BS09	Review the charging points in the booking service app
BS10	Synchronize the booked sessions and your calendar and have a reminder of the booked sessions
BS11	Manage your booked session (edit, cancel...)
BS12	Start and stop the charging session using the booking app

Table 5 Discrete analysis for the booking service in Bari

CODE	M	P	A	I	Q	R	CATEGORY
BS01	10	10	60	50	0	0	Attractive
BS02	10	20	60	40	0	0	Attractive
BS03	0	30	70	30	0	0	Attractive
BS04	0	10	90	20	0	10	Attractive
BS05	10	0	40	80	0	0	Indifferent
BS06	20	40	40	30	0	0	Perf. / Attr.
BS07	0	0	70	60	0	0	Attractive
BS08	70	40	0	20	0	0	Must-be
BS09	0	0	80	40	0	10	Attractive
BS10	0	20	60	40	0	0	Attractive
BS11	10	30	60	30	0	0	Attractive
BS12	10	0	50	70	0	0	Indifferent

Table 5 shows that most of the responders find attractive the functionalities BS01, BS02, BS03, BS04, BS07, BS09 and BS10. It is noted that the results of the survey analysis reporting the user perception of the service have been considered for prioritizing the features implementation of the described services.

In the metropolitan city of Bari pilot site, the booking service is offered by the Polytechnic University of Bari connected as electromobility service provider to local CPOs through the Hsubject eRoaming platform, which is one of the largest in Europe. The booking service is interoperable, and it is designed and developed for offering to users' short term and long term reservation options, based on enhanced offline and real time information, such as the presence of PoI close the CP, the status of the CP and the real-time cost of a recharge. It is possible to book a charge point from a list of available CPs based on the specific travel needs. Using a mobile application, the user can book the recharge session, and monitor in real time the energy and cost status of the recharge (see Figure 1). Recently, the demonstration of this service has been launched to a selected pool of end users in the university staff and real data collection just started. The IMP, whose functionalities are described in Section 2.3, will be connected to the booking service platform, and demonstrated soon to incentivize a fair and ethical use of the booking and the charging stations.

4. Conclusions

The push for decarbonization in the transportation sector reflects a collective commitment to combat climate change and create a sustainable future. European and global objectives are aligned in prioritizing the development and adoption of innovative, low-carbon technologies and policies to transform the way we move people and goods. In this paper, in the context of the H2020 EU eCharge4Drivers project, enhanced electromobility services are presented which have been developed with the objective of improving the EV user charging experiences and incentivize the use of electric mobility. The described services have been a priori evaluated by users in the Italian pilot site of the metropolitan city of Bari which is a large area in the southern Italy.

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